

EXTENDED FINITE ELEMENT METHOD MODELING OF CRACK PATHS IN PARTICLE REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

Understanding the fracture behavior of the particle reinforced composites is vitally important to developing high performance materials for technological applications. Studies of the interaction between cracks and particles have received much attention in previous years. Analytical approaches have been developed for problems concerning cracks inside, outside, penetrating or lying along the interface of various types of particles. However, all these analyses are based on the assumption of a given crack location and size, or a prescribed crack path which is known a priori, due to the symmetry of the particular problem. More general situations should be with the help of numerical methods, including the finite element related methods (FEM) and the boundary element related methods (BEM). By enriching the standard approximation with additional functions, the extended finite element method (XFEM) allows for the modeling of arbitrary geometric features independently of the finite element mesh. This advance has provided a convenient computational tool for modeling discontinuities and their evolvment. However, in XFEM modeling of discontinuous problems, the corresponding analytical results are pre-requisite. If the analytical solutions are difficult to obtain or are very complex themselves, the application is not easy. In present work, an improved extended finite element method, which synchronously extracts the advantages of the FEM and the XFEM, is developed. By this method, we investigate the interaction between a propagating crack and a single particle or multiple particles in a brittle matrix. The objectives are to study the effects of particle amount, location and material mismatch on crack path.

2 Improved Extended Finite Element Method

By enriching the standard approximation with additional functions, the extended finite element method allows for the modeling of arbitrary geometric features independently of the finite element mesh. This advance has provided a robust and accurate computational tool for modeling discontinuities and their evolvment.

In the present work, the extended finite method without tip-enriched functions is employed. Fig.1 (a) illustrates the different discontinuous interfaces in a domain Ω and Fig.1 (b) shows the finite element mesh and refined mesh around crack tips. The crack surfaces are assumed to be traction-free. Different from conventional XFEM, in present work only the straightforward enrichment functions for material interfaces and crack surfaces are adopted. In order to improve the numerical precision, the mesh around the crack tips is refined as shown in Fig.1 (b). The degenerate elements are employed around the crack tips just like the idea used in the traditional finite element method. Thus, this method can easily be applied to the problems in which the analytical expressions of crack tip field are difficult to obtain or are complex themselves.

Fig.1. (a) Illustration of different discontinuous interfaces in a domain Ω ; (b) Finite element mesh and refined mesh around crack tips.

3 Implementation of the Numerical Method

For crack-growth modeling in particle reinforced composites, the processes of numerical calculation

are as following. First, the location of the refined mesh are directly associated with the location of the crack tip during the simulation. Then, the domain occupied by elements around the tip-element and the tip-element (in this paper, 9 elements as shown in Fig.1 (b) are adopted) is refined as mentioned above. Finally, the refined mesh over the original structured mesh will be laid. They share the same nodes with each other on the boundary of the refined domain. The initial values of stiffness of the 9 original quadrilateral elements are assigned to zero, and will not be computed any more. These manipulations insure that only the refined mesh works in the refined domain and the structured mesh is not destroyed during the crack-growth modeling. With this method, only small region should be refined and there is no need to ensure the crack surfaces and the material interfaces confirm with the mesh boundaries.

Consequently, we adopt the approximation of the displacement $u(x)$ as:

$$\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}) = \sum N_I(\mathbf{x})\mathbf{u}_I + \sum_{i=1}^2 \sum N_{J,i}(\mathbf{x})\mathbf{b}_{J,i}\psi_{J,i}(\mathbf{x}) + \sum_{j=1}^2 \sum N_{K,j}(\mathbf{x})\mathbf{c}_{K,j}\varphi_{K,j}(\mathbf{x})$$

Here, $N(x)$ is the standard finite element shape function; $\psi_J(x)$ and $\varphi_K(x)$ are the shifted enrichment functions for cracks and material interfaces, respectively; \mathbf{b}_J and \mathbf{c}_K are the additional degrees of freedom for the corresponding enriched nodes. Of course, there are several similar choices for the enriched functions.

4 The interaction integral

The interaction integral is derived from the J-integral for two admissible states (actual and auxiliary fields). Through appropriate algebraic manipulations, this method can easily decouple the mixed-mode stress intensity factors. If we choose the incompatibility formulation of the auxiliary fields, the expression of the interactions integral could be changed. The new expression of the interaction integral does not contain any derivatives of material properties. As a result, the interaction integral does not need the material properties to be differentiable. Since it may be difficult to obtain the derivatives of material properties or there are no derivatives in actual case. Furthermore, the interaction integral is still valid even when the integral domain contains material interfaces.

5 The maximum hoop stress criterion

There are several criteria for predicting crack growth direction in non-homogeneous materials. The maximum hoop stress criterion, which is a commonly used criterion, is adopted herein. According to this criterion, the crack will grow in the direction along which the maximum hoop stress occurs. Namely, once $K > K_{IC}$, the crack grows in the direction by a small increment set in advance and the process repeated.

6 Numerical examples

In order to demonstrate the accuracy of the numerical technique proposed in this paper, we present some numerical examples of crack-particle interaction in particulate-reinforced composite materials. The static/dynamic stress intensity factors are presented to demonstrate the static/dynamic interaction effects on the crack-tip field for various locations and material combinations.

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